

EIJASTR

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED SCIENCES AND THEORETICAL RESEARCH

International Scientific Journal

2026

European International Journal Of Applied Sciences And Theoretical Research

Volume 02, Issue 06

EDITORIAL BOARD:**Professor Emma Franke**

Editor in Chief

Prof. Jo Coldwell-Neilson

Associate Editor In Chief Deakin University, Australia

Mr Mohd Helmy

Abd Wahab Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Shafi'i Muhammad Abdulhamid

Federal University Of Technology Minna, Nigeria., Nigeria

Dr Man Fung (Kelvin) Lo

The Chinese University Of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Dr Ahmad Samed

Al-Adwan Al Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Waleed Alsabhan

Kacst, Saudi Arabia Yvonne Antonucci Widener University, United States

Prof. Orit Avidov Ungar

Achva Academic College & Open University Of Israel, Israel

Dr. Aslina Baharum

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia

ON SOME TERMS AND CONCEPTS IN ETHNOLOGY

Ulugbek Abdullayev

Professor, Doctor of Historical Sciences,
Andijan State Technical Institute.

Abstract: This article provides a scholarly analysis of frequently used terms in ethnology such as ethnogenesis, ethnogenetic processes, ethnic history, ethnicity, ethnic group, and ethnographic group. The article also reveals the essence of scholarly-theoretical approaches to the formation of peoples — primordialism, constructivism, and instrumentalism — as well as the views put forward by theorists belonging to these schools.

Keywords: Ethnogenesis, ethnic history, ethnogenetic process, ethnicity, ethnic group, ethnographic group, primordialism, constructivism

There are a number of terms and concepts related to the origin of a people and their ethno-culture. A clear understanding of their meaning is important for a comprehensive scholarly analysis of the ethnogenetic processes and ethno-culture of any given ethnos. The most frequently used term in ethnology is "ethnogenesis."

Ethnogenesis – the term comes from Greek: *ethnos* (ἔθνος) meaning "people" and *genesis* (γένεσις) meaning "origin." Many definitions have been given to the term. According to the prominent ethnologist and academician K. Shoniyazov, "...ethnogenesis refers to the emergence of a new ethnos (nation) on the basis of several previously existing ethnic components." [1].

Thus, ethnogenesis is a concept referring to the origin and genealogical emergence of a particular people. Once a new ethnos emerges, the ethnic markers characteristic of the previous ethnic community gradually disappear (for example, the Sakas, Massagetae, Tokharians, and others), or the ethnic markers are partially preserved even as the ethnic composition changes. Academician A. Askarov divides the process of people-formation into three successive stages: ethnogenesis, ethnic history, and national history. He emphasizes that each of these stages — ethnogenesis, ethnic history, and national history — has both a starting and an ending point. The starting point of ethnogenesis traces back to the distant "ancestors" of the ethnos. The ethnogenesis process continues until a given ethnic community takes shape as a distinct nation. Once a people has formed as a distinct nation, its ethnic history begins.

The ethnogenetic process refers to the formation of a people's earliest roots. It is a long-lasting historical and ethno-cultural process. In this process, ethnic groups

differing in physical appearance, language, and material and spiritual culture gradually come closer together, intermingle, and develop common ethnic characteristics. The Uzbek people also, as a result of a long ethnogenetic process, assimilated various ethnic components into their ethnic composition and first formed as a nation (elat) and later as a nationality (millat)..

Ethnic History – encompasses the period from the earliest ancestors of a particular people, including the formation of the nation (elat), the stages of its development, and the period of its dissolution.

Ethnicity – a concept concerned with studying problems of polyethnic ethnoses or conflicting situations in inter-ethnic relations at the regional level. From the 1960s onward, the term "ethnicity" began to be used in Western social (cultural) anthropology. Entering the discipline from the English language, the term became widespread in European social anthropology by the last quarter of the 20th century, and was used as a "new concept" in the work "Introduction. Ethnicity: Theory and Experience" published by N. Glazer and D. Moynihan in 1975. An analysis of scholarly literature shows that to this day there is no unified, generalized definition of the true meaning of this term. Most researchers offer the following definition: ethnicity is the totality of cultural characteristics belonging to a particular ethnic group — that is, ethnicity is a form of social organization of cultural differences. [2].

Ethnic Group – a distinct part of a people or nation living in the territory of another state or within a different ethno-cultural environment, having preserved certain elements of lifestyle and culture (its own language, distinctive features of material and spiritual culture, religion, etc.).

Ethnographic Group – one of the subdivisions that forms an integral part of a given ethnos (nation or nationality), distinguished by some of its characteristics such as dialect, economic activity, and certain aspects of its way of life. Historically, the Kipchaks, Turks, Yuzs, and Kuramas within the Uzbek people were considered ethnographic groups.

Ethnic Tradition – a combination of stereotypes and behavioral norms, cultural canons, political and economic forms, and worldviews specific to a particular ethnic group, passed down from generation to generation.

It should be noted that today ever newer views on the formation of peoples are being put forward. Among them, the scholarly-theoretical approaches of primordialism (from Latin "primordial" – "primordial," "initial," "original") or essentialism, constructivism (from Latin "constructa" – structure), and instrumentalism (from Latin "instrumentum" – "tool," "instrument") have become widely established in academic discourse. Theorists belonging to these scholarly-theoretical schools provide various definitions of ethnic issues.

According to scholars belonging to the primordialism school, an ethnos or ethnicity is a concrete phenomenon with an objective basis in nature or society — a historically formed group of people, manifesting as a common language, territorial unity, economic life and psychological community based on cultural integrity, a

product of the biogeographic sphere, a real reality that has undergone a long process spanning several stages of ethnogenesis. Adherents of this approach emphasize that an ethnos or ethnicity is a concrete phenomenon with an objective basis in nature or society. Representatives of this approach include Western scholars R. Gambino, E. Wolf, C. Geertz, W. Connor, P. Van den Berghe, A. Greeley, G. Parsons, Russian ethnographers and historians L. Gumilyov, S. Shirokogorov, Yu. Bromley, and local scholars K. Shoniyazov, I. Jabborov, and A. Askarov.

Supporters of constructivism reject the idea that ethnos and nations emerge based on principles of historicity, or that they are products of the biogeographic sphere and a real reality that has passed through a long, multi-stage process. Instead, they argue that the historical-social reality associated with the ethnos is a result of human imagination — an artificial socio-intellectual construct created by Soviet theorists. Western scholars B. Anderson, E. Gellner, F. Barth, E. Hobsbawm, Soviet and Russian researchers V. Tishkov, V. Voronkov, V. Malakhov, S. Kardinskaya, E. Belkova, Yu. Oleynikov, S. Madyukova, K. Reznikova, and local scholars A. Ilkhomov, V. Khan, I. Khujakhanov are among the supporters of this view.

According to proponents of the instrumentalist approach, the policies pursued by governments, state administrative bodies, or leading individuals served as the primary instrument in the formation of various peoples or nations. In other words, according to instrumentalism, "ethnicity" is a sense of "solidarity" within a group of people formed as a result of particular circumstances. A society formed on the basis of ethnicity is a tool used by various elites, groups, or individuals to achieve their goals. Among the proponents of this approach we may point to scholars such as L. Bell, N. Glazer, J. De Vos, A. Peterson-Royce, A. Cohen, D. Moynihan, J. Nagel, D. Horowitz, and S. Ozlak. This theoretical view was not only supported but also developed to a certain extent by Russian researchers such as V. Yadov, Z. Sikevich, M. Guboglo, and L. Drobizheva.

In conclusion, while today's scholarship offers a wide variety of approaches concerning the origin, meaning, essence, and definition of terms and concepts related to the formation of peoples, debates in this field continue to this day.

REFERENCES

1. Шониёзов К. “Ўзбек халқининг шаклланиши жараёни”. Т: 2001. В.77
2. Аширов А. “Этнология” Т: 2014. В.124-124